

Data Management for Materials Researchers

Henry Royce Institute Workshop – 14th January 2022

Workshop Notes

Sponsored by the MIDAS and Lightform programme grants, this workshop was aimed at materials science researchers (from any discipline) who collect, store, analyse and share experimental data associated with their samples. It also welcomed inputs from research data management/data infrastructure researchers and specialists. The workshop shared examples of best practice and current initiatives in the area, with the aim of generating discussion and producing a list of actions to enable better data management practices for materials science.

Improving data management and sharing culture requires the involvement of everyone in the community and so the meeting was open to all, at all career stages, from all institutions and backgrounds. Discussions were moderated to ensure that everyone had the opportunity to contribute.

The workshop was based around discussions of questions, stimulated by short talks from speakers. The following are notes summarising the discussions. They are not a perfect record of everything that was discussed, but nevertheless, it is hoped they prove a useful resource for further activity in this area.

These notes have been compiled by multiple authors, and summarise contributions from many more people, and are owned by the community.

Many thanks to all those who took part in the workshop and contributed to this write up.

QUESTION 1: Why should data management be important to materials science researchers?	<i>Speaker 1 [10 mins]: Andrew Stewart, UoM</i> <i>Speaker 2 [10 mins]: Richard Broadbent, Rolls Royce</i> <i>Discussion [20 mins]</i>
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Research reproducibility

Transparency in research data and methods, models used, code and operating systems is integral for the data to be (re)useable/understandable by other researchers. This allows for robust reproducibility and transparent quality of research and even propagation of best practice. In order for this to happen data should be FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable.

Research councils and funders are moving towards policies of open research, not just open access to the results in the form of an article. The adherence to policies is not regularly policed by these bodies, and there is little oversight of compliance for grant holders. Similarly in academic journals, open data is promoted but often not mandatory for publication.

Longevity of Use and Legacy Data

Data can be expensive to generate, especially for destructive tests. The large quantities of data generated from these needs to be findable and usable for up to 100 years in some industrial cases. New analysis methods often mean that past data can be re-analysed for improved information extraction.

Legacy data can be challenging to process as it is often stored with varying levels of traceability and useability. To reshape this into something usable is a significant undertaking.

Perhaps roles such as data stewards and curators could improve archived data, and in the future perhaps AI could also be used for curation. Again, a dedicated resource such as this is expensive, and not all groups/companies are willing to invest.

Decisions on what we upload/save is all data worth saving?

Data storage is expensive, however, and so should all data be stored? Data can be produced at varying levels of quality. So, how do we decide if it is worth saving and sharing? It is still important to share even “standard” or “stable” data as results reproduced by different labs can be done with varying degrees of success or widely varying values and results, and even the most “stable” results can change when carried out in different environments/by different people. Quality standards for the data and good descriptions of, and comments on, the data are key in this case so that any potential user is aware of quality and limitations.

Reduction in repetition of experiments

Reproducibility and repetition of experiments costing time and money, publishing data moves us towards accountability.

Associated references/links:

UKRI Open Research Policy:

<https://www.ukri.org/our-work/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/open-research/>

Journal article on improving research:

<https://bmcrenotes.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13104-021-05883-3>

Example of data stewardship at TU Delft:

<https://embassy.science/wiki/Theme:D44f7704-4e28-484c-a137-fbb2bb44836b>

Docker, software to manage computer environments:

<https://medium.com/the-andela-way/docker-for-beginners-61e8e0ce6a19>

QUESTION 2:**What data should materials scientists capture, and how should they be stored***Speaker 1 [10 mins]: Ben Thomas**Speaker 2 [10 mins]: Joe Kelleher**Discussion [20 mins]***The materials research data landscape**

Data is generated throughout the scientific process in materials science – from hypothesis through to final analysis. There are numerous forms of data and metadata that are generated during a typical investigation, for example:

- Input material metadata (e.g., composition, processing history, storage history, etc)
- Processing data (e.g., recorded load during rolling) and metadata (e.g., calibrations).
- Sample preparation metadata (e.g., parameters used for cutting).
- Other sample metadata (e.g., extraction location)
- Characterisation data (e.g., optical images) and metadata (e.g., calibrations and parameters).
- Analysis data (e.g., grain sizes) and metadata (e.g., analysis codes and parameters).
- Simulation data. There are several initiatives dealing with simulation data in materials science.

The data and metadata associated with even a single investigation are typically diverse in many respects – e.g., whether text-based or numeric, their file formats, whether they are recorded in a structured or unstructured form, etc. This complexity is a challenge to our data management ambitions.

The particular mix of data we capture often varies depending on the scale of the facilities used. For instance, universities typically host small-scale facilities comprising many pieces of equipment under one roof. Here, small quantities of data from multiple pieces of equipment are commonplace and there is typically a mix of structured and unstructured data. At larger-scale facilities (e.g., ISIS, Diamond) there tend to be fewer types of measurement being taken, but far larger quantities of data generated from each capability. Furthermore, this tends to be captured in a more structured way than in the lab.

Capturing and storing our data

Capturing as much data (and metadata) as possible at every stage of our investigations is attractive for many reasons, most of which hinge on the notion that we do not necessarily know which data/metadata are going to be important at a later date - for instance, capturing lots of data is likely to enable additional unforeseen analyses, improve the interrogatability of the dataset by machine learning techniques, and allow for more effective sharing and reanalysis externally. We should work towards creating research environments in which data (and metadata) are acquired and stored *automatically* by the equipment we use, and we reduce the burden of human effort (although data checking and curation will still be critical). Should we be specifying automatic data recording capabilities when we purchase new pieces of equipment? Should our funders insist that any equipment bought with public funds is able to export data in an open format or be accessible via an API?

There are concerns that some important metadata is often difficult to capture or lost entirely. For instance, qualitative observations (e.g., “it made a funny noise...”) and routine maintenance (e.g., the data one bulb was replaced for a notionally identical one, software updates, etc) are often not recorded or reported. Being too structured when recording our metadata could be an obstacle to this – we need to have flexibility to add new fields, etc. For qualitative observations, a further complication is the lack of a common language when reporting (e.g., what is meant by a “funny” noise?). Interdisciplinary work can help contribute to the development of common languages.

Sample preparation metadata is something we’re not very good at capturing – the lack of standard protocols (and/or adherence to them) is problematic. There may be solutions in terms of developing and sharing more rigid protocols¹. Also, there are a few options for electronic lab books² – perhaps graphical-based data structures are preferable to SQL.

Capturing metadata is critically important for adoption and reanalysis of data by other parties. We should strive for completeness in this as well as in our data. E.g., aspects of sample preparation or historic equipment use might be of vital importance to correctly interpret a result. However, there is likely a balance to be struck here - we should also recognise that sometimes it is very challenging to acquire complete metadata, and this should not be viewed as a hard barrier to someone sharing their data (more sharing is generally a good thing).

Our methods of storing data, and filtering/organising captured data prior to storage, are of great importance if we are to realise the full potential of our datasets. Effective storage does have expenses associated with it (e.g., in terms of curation man hours, energy consumption – esp. if on the cloud), so we must make sure we are diligent in this matter. Our actions will depend on the following principal considerations (which we will need to anticipate in advance): what data people will want, how they will want to interact with it, and what analyses they will perform on it. We then need to work out storage schemes that most effectively meet these considerations.

Can we make our storage schemes more standardised? For instance, should we insist on a move away from spreadsheets and text files towards queryable structured databases? Is there a balance between completeness and ease of population (e.g., just store all files) vs. ease to query/search (structured tables and databases)? Standardising practices will be difficult owing to the diversity of our data. One potential avenue of exploration is storing data in reference to a time series (a sample history) – could we store all data against the time at which it was gathered? Another suggestion regarding metadata is that they could be captured in a resource description framework (RDF) and stored using the linked-data paradigm, to generate a knowledge graph (this approach is now being used in the life sciences). Efforts regarding standardisation of metadata are already in progress in the US³ and elsewhere^{4,5}.

Should datasets associated with ‘failures’ be stored? The answer depends on what is meant by a ‘failure’. If high-quality data has failed to show an anticipated result, then this should still be viewed as good data and retained (e.g., for machine learning analyses). Conversely, if

there has been a failure of the technique or approach used (e.g., the camera has not been focused), then this data is unlikely to be very useful. Limited examples of such failures could be used for training purposes, but otherwise effort should not be spent on retaining the associated data.

Associated references/links:

¹<https://www.protocols.io/>

²

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/advanced-research-computing/platforms/research-data-services/ucl-electronic-research-notebook>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Directed_acyclic_graph

<https://citrineinformatics.github.io/gemd-docs/>

³<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/working-group-international-materials-resource-registries.html>

⁴ExPaNDS (<https://expands.eu/>) and PaNOSC (<https://www.panosc.eu/>) (metadata and services for photon and neutron data)

⁵<https://citrineinformatics.github.io/gemd-docs/>

Points falling under another of the questions:

[Regarding open analysis software, Q3] A lot of companies have software with limited, payable licenses. So, unless you will buy their software you cannot access the data. Then, if companies cannot make money on making software, will they try to improve it?

[Regarding ontology for materials, Q4]

https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/RDA_December-Interm_Birkholz_2021.pdf

<https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

<p>QUESTION 3: How should data processing and analysis considerations influence our data management practices (capture, storage, sharing)?</p>	<p><i>Speaker 1 [10 mins]: Adam Plowman</i> <i>Speaker 2 [10 mins]: Tim Dodwell</i> <i>Discussion [20 mins]</i></p>
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We should be guided by use cases:

- What we store and how we store it should enable the uses we want to put data to.
- Amongst these are visualisation, analysis, inter-comparison, sharing and reuse, reproducibility, automation of decisions...
- Storage capacity, in most cases, is unlikely to be an issue. We should also store simulation data and data from failed experiments.
- We should not let our pre-conceived notions of what aspects of the data contain information dictate what we store (others might have a different view and we also then reduce the capacity for data science to extract new knowledge)
- Can the data be reproduced (rather than stored), is the data analysis reproducible (or do we need to store data at intermediate steps in the analysis process), do we need the raw data (can we sometimes undertake significant processing before storage and be certain of no great information loss)?
- Often our analysis of data is focused on answering a simple question (e.g. at what temperature should I process my alloy?) but often we need to interpret data in a more holistic way, balancing weight of evidence to propose and support a narrative hypothesis (our “mechanistic explanations”). These might demand different approaches.
- Systems need to be adaptable and to grow and change as use cases emerge. We shouldn’t lock out future use cases by being overly prescriptive about what is stored and how.
- Building common APIs, aggregation tools, data creation and analysis workflows, etc is more achievable than getting everyone to agree to a single format, use a single database etc.

Metadata is key:

- It needs to be explicit and readable, by machines and humans.
- The breadth of the metadata should support as many possible use cases as possible, not focus only on the immediate intentions of the data collector
- We need to tackle the issue of proprietary metadata formats. Funders can play a role in driving instrument manufacturers towards best practice.

Analysis considerations should shape collection and storage:

- The majority of time in a data-science project is spent collating and cleaning data. Getting collection right would make this much more efficient. Once the data is in the right form, it is easy to try out many techniques.
- In materials science we will almost always be working in a “spare data” regime, because of the richness and complexity of the materials space. This increases the need for sharing. <https://virtual.oxfordabstracts.com/#/event/3101/submission/52>

- We should consider the possibilities of more varied data analysis (e.g. functional data analysis).
- Engage with a data scientist *before* commencing data collection.

We need to train materials scientists in data science

- Training in experimental design, modern data analysis (which is more fun than boring old stats), use of electronic lab-books is a must, especially in a world where experimental data generation is inherently digital.
- Our funders could encourage this (e.g., in the next round of CDTs).

Associated references/links:

- Highlights the costs of data sharing as well as benefits:
<https://febs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/1873-3468.14067>
- Useful guide on how to name files so that they are easier for humans and computers to work with:
<https://speakerdeck.com/jennybc/how-to-name-files>
- Example of approach to unifying multiple disparate datasets (in materials modelling in this case)
<https://www.optimade.org>
- Survey of data scientists:
<https://www.anaconda.com/state-of-data-science-2020>
- Reference in consideration of issue of overly prescriptive database design:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337336089_Concept-oriented_model_Modeling_and_processing_data_using_functions
- Addressing what we might learn from business – a 2017 blogpost by Maxime Beauchemin "The Rise of the Data Engineer":
<https://www.freecodecamp.org/news/the-rise-of-the-data-engineer-91be18f1e603/>
- "Hiring a statistician after the data have been collected is like hiring a physician when the patient is in the morgue. He may be able to tell you what went wrong, but he is unlikely to be able to fix it." - Ronald A. Fisher (1938)

Points falling under another of the questions:

- [Culture change, Q5] How do we ensure credit for data production and sharing in a world where data production and data analysis are often going on in separate groups?
- [Culture change, Q5] Research outputs other than just papers need to be recognised.

QUESTION 4:
How should we store our research data, and when should we delete them?

Speaker 1 [10 mins]: Bill Ayres
Speaker 2 [10 mins]: Norman Paton
Discussion [20 mins]

Why share research data

Sharing of data is of critical importance to the scientific endeavour in general; from understanding repeatability and experimental validity to peer reviewing and enabling collaborations.

- Increased Impact – collaborations, credit from other scholars using it, increased citations, policy making and legislation
- Promotes transparency
- Increasing number of funders requiring data publication – REF likely to be exploring this further in the next exercise
- UKRI Open Access Policy – data access statement is now mandatory
- Social responsibility

Open Data Repositories

- Most universities offer open data repositories, to store, manage and publish curated data.
- Funders and publishers may provide a separate platform/repository
- Largest directory: [re3Data](#)
- Other examples: [Dryad](#), [Open Science Framework](#) (OSF), [Zenodo](#), [figshare.com](#), [NOMAD](#), [Materials Cloud](#)
- Figshare at the University of Manchester used as a demonstration – repository that allows sharing with guests as well (as long as they have a figshare.com account)

Benefits of Using Open Data Repositories

Data repositories offer a safe, secure platform to preserve, store and publish key data whilst also allowing the addition of metadata to facilitate discovery and reuse. Repositories provide a unique and persistent doi for each dataset enabling easy linking on publications, presentations, and any dissemination activities. Furthermore, full integrations with ancillary services such as Github and ORCID provide improved indexing for discoverability and impact.

Lessons from Other Disciplines

Whilst data storage and sharing is becoming more of a consideration in materials science, insights from other disciplines, such as the biological sciences, can prove beneficial in the design of systems and protocols that are functional for materials science.

Cost of Data Storage

The real cost of data storage depends on the manual effort needed to get the data in a usable and reusable state, particularly as associated with metadata and not the data itself. Furthermore, different data will incur different costs. Factors to consider when evaluating the costs of data storage are: metadata required for experimental process and sample, data itself, human consumer, software consumer, output metadata. However, it should be clear what the benefits expected are from the different costs, particularly as often the benefits are derived by the people that don't pay the costs. Reducing the costs or passing on the

costs from the individual to larger organisations/consortia allows the benefits to become more apparent. This is a topic of particular interest that forms part of the cultural changes required in the field (addressed under Question 5, below).

How the data is consumed should also be a critical consideration as the human vs. machine consumer will necessitate different characteristics from the data itself. It is anticipated that establishing robust archiving practices can provide avenues for more data-centric engineering processes.

Longevity and duration of data storage

A key question arising from the discussion on data repositories is the length of time over which data is stored and termination policies that may delete datasets after a pre-determined period of time. Related to this is the deposition of curated datasets on multiple platforms that may lead to additional issues of automatic scrapers “overcounting” datasets, as well as environmental concerns of data storage.

Is there a need for a “materials specific” repository?

The lessons from the biological sciences seem to suggest that developing protocols for data capture and storage is a useful tool in enabling a culture change. Given the broadness of techniques and data used in materials science, is there a need to develop discipline specific repositories? The suggestion from other disciplines is to come together as a community to start identifying specific techniques and data types that can be easily standardised to accelerate the cultural change and put the necessary infrastructure in place.

Importance of Standards

Standardisation of processes for data storage is an ongoing discussion. Lessons from other disciplines suggest that discussions on standardisation allow the small shifts necessary to understand what works and enable wider cultural changes.

Infrastructure & data projects

- PSDI: initiative which aims to build a national physical data infrastructure for the physical sciences. This is currently in the pilot phase with funding from UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure. The current pilot phase aims to conduct trials and consultations to decide on the priorities for the next phase. The project aims to mix data scientists and scientists across the physical sciences domain. If interested, please do get in touch with Barbara Montanari (XXXXXX) if you want to know more or input directly in what the PSDI should deliver to enable, among other things, a federated materials database.
- FAIR-DI: “Such data infrastructure enables extensive data sharing and collaborations in data-driven sciences, including artificial intelligence, and it expands basic science and engineering. FAIR-DI engages with scientists across generations to promote innovations and further careers, and it reaches out to industry and society.”
<https://www.fair-di.eu/fairmat/consortium>
- German NFDI initiative: “funding to make data from various scientific disciplines uniformly and systematically accessible. The consistent and barrier-free standardization of data by researchers and scientific institutions will enable significant efficiency gains and synergies between individual researchers and

appropriately developed IT systems. In times of digital infrastructures, this step is central to the way we will conduct research in the future.” Within this initiative, discipline specific groups are starting to emerge, including in materials:
nfdi-matwerk.de

Should all data be shared, and if so, when and where?	<i>Open Discussion [40 mins]</i>
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Although there are many benefits to data sharing, it should be borne in mind that the good data management practices required for data sharing are worth adopting, even if the data is only shared within a limited group of, for example only with close collaborators. There is often support at the library that can be used, there could be more support, for example by data engineers in institutions, embedded in research teams. Grants should cost research software engineers and data engineers, who should have full career paths.

Culture change is very difficult, and it should be noted that materials data is very heterogeneous (as it is in other fields). We should learn why initiatives like the materials genome have not been more successful. Building on previous initiatives should take into account more recent developments in data science., and extract the extra value that exists in the heterogeneous nature of the data.

People needed for data sharing and management are both people developing the software (and maintaining hardware) and those making these resources work for researchers and training them.

One barrier to culture change is that people making decisions now have had successful careers without sharing data and therefore find it more difficult to see the value and push change. For example, data management and curating takes time and slows science down, but at the same time this comes from a focus on the quantity of results instead of the quality of results.

Materials scientists must understand what they gain from sharing data, this is not very clear yet. In particular, the benefits of sharing are not obvious to early career researchers and students. How can this be changed? Scientific outputs other than paper authorship need to be recognized: protocols, data and software should be recognized as valuable outputs. Could also be part of PhD training. An institution that is working in things connected to these issues is the Software Sustainability Institute <https://www.software.ac.uk/>.

An important benefit for early career researchers is that data (and code) sharing means your research becomes portable, so they travel with you when you move and access to it is not controlled by anyone else.

Funders could enforce data management more strictly and reward data sharing but there is a fear that this creates a big barrier to ongoing research.. EPSRC is reluctant to make fast hard changes and are worried about impact on the community, but are keen to develop a

data management policy. Some worries about sustainability. Some funding for data sharing infrastructure would also be welcome since a shared repository can help drive culture change. EPSRC is supportive of RSE and would be keen to encourage data scientist recognition in academia. Training in data management, and data management expectation for progression in CDTs would be very welcome in a future CDT bid for example. Currently, lack of resources inhibits auditing by the research council, but perhaps this could be moved to universities?

Why don't people share the data - is it too difficult? Perhaps because data shared currently cannot be used properly and its value fully realised. To make published data valuable, curators are important. A place for the data was very important in Life Sciences. Is the situation in materials science immature, or is it more complex (heterogeneous data).

Commercial funded data is usually not made available, even in the life sciences. But this is improving and there are new initiatives to release previously restricted data.

QUESTION 5:
What cultural changes are needed to facilitate our data management ambitions?

Speaker 1: Sandra Korte-Kerzel

Speaker 2: Alice Pyne

- *Tom Hancocks*

Ultimately, the success of data sharing initiatives depends on the people doing the data management. Even in fields where data sharing is established like biology, it is difficult to get PhD students interested in data management and sharing and quite a challenge to make them understand why it is important (although there are certainly things we can learn from other fields like biology).

Networks for data sharing have been set up in Germany, with agreed metadata schemes agreed on by the community. However, when used by researchers many data fields are unused and instead information is entered in the “comments” box. There is a need to make uploading easier/automatic, to lower the barrier.

We should appreciate efforts of doing data management and sharing well, and create incentives for it. Starting is going to be very difficult and those who start may not see much benefit. However we should bear in mind that many people doing research will not go on to academic careers and so incentives like citations and career progression in academia might not always work.

Software is also an important part of data sharing and software sharing has similarities to data sharing. We shouldn't let doing it perfectly get in the way of starting to share data/software. We should spread awareness of the tools available for sharing software and data.

Engaging learned societies can be a powerful way to start sharing software and data and so can dedicated meetings. Bringing people into your project and incorporating their contributions is another great way of building a network.

People would share data if other people used it. Centralised repositories would help with this. And funder mandated data access statements could help push people into sharing their data more freely. Also, auditing of data access compliance could be a very powerful way of changing culture and funders should consider it.

Data management should be part of the infrastructure or research environment, it should be difficult NOT to manage data properly at the point of collection.

The research supervisor/manager also has a role of being more active during data acquisition and analysis to ensure it is being done in a shareable and reproducible way.

There should be a collection of good examples of data management and sharing practice that others can emulate, perhaps hosted by Royce or another community institution.

More formal training on data management would be welcome by PhD students, and also by the industrial partners hiring PhD graduates.

As reviewers we can also start asking for data and code to be made available.

Materials made smarter (<https://www.madesmarter.uk/>) has academic psychologists on the research team studying how the culture can be effectively changed.

We should also consider inclusivity in the space of data management and how do we make sure it is a comfortable space for everyone, including disabled people. Initiatives like “How-to-guides” that improve accessibility to people from different backgrounds should be prioritized.